

Aluminium Powder as a Synthetic Reagent.

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Since the middle of the 19th century, various metals have been used in the different processes of organic synthesis, but the metal aluminium has not received as wide applications although its salts, particularly the anhydrous chloride and to a certain extent the amalgam have been used in the well-known Friedel-Craft's synthesis. Perhaps the first important attempts to treat metallic aluminium with organic substances were those of Gladstone and Tribe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1876, 29, 158; 1881, 39, 1) who prepared aluminium alcoholates by the action of alcohols on the metal. Their work was subsequently extended and criticised by Saligman and Williams (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 113, 159), who prepared the aluminium salts of fatty acids, alcohols and phenols by the action of purified aluminium powder on the corresponding dry substances at their respective boiling points. They also showed that the reactions are entirely inhibited by traces of moisture even when once started, and this phenomenon has been explained by them as due to the formation of a superficial layer of oxide.

In 1895, an attempt was made by Radziewanoski (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1139) to use aluminium powder mixed with mercuric chloride as a condensing agent in the ordinary Friedel-Craft's reaction, but it was a failure. Later on he found (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1560) that aluminium powder in benzene or xylene solution formed compounds with mercuric chloride of the type $C_6H_5 \cdot AlCl_2 \cdot HgCl$, which gave successful results in several condensations of the type of Friedel-Craft's reaction. Subsequently, this work has been extended by Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1335).

The above represents practically the whole of the literature on the reactions of aluminium powder, from which it can be easily seen that aluminium powder has hardly been used in the condensations apparently due to its inactivity, and in those few scattered examples in which use has been made of the metal, it has been either amalgamated with mercury or mixed with such substances as mercuric chloride or hydrogen chloride. Therefore the present investigation was undertaken with a view to make an

exhaustive study of the metal in many of the typical reactions of organic chemistry.

It was found that ordinary aluminium powder is very inactive. Washing with caustic soda and acid, refluxing for several hours with ether, alcohol or benzene did not make much improvement. The problem was becoming almost hopeless, when incidentally it was found that aluminium powder becomes highly reactive when heated in a current of pure dry hydrogen at about 500° for a short time. This peculiar phenomenon was at first thought to be due to the formation of a metallic hydride, but since on quantitative analysis the metal thus activated is found to contain no hydrogen, it is supposed that the activation is due to the reduction of the film of suboxide with which the surface of ordinary metallic aluminium is always covered. The existence of such a suboxide has not been recorded in inorganic literature, the only oxide on record being Al_2O_3 . But as it is well known that the latter oxide cannot be reduced by hydrogen, so the presence of a sub-oxide is fairly tentative as in the case of lead. Aluminium thus activated has been found to react vigorously with oxygenated and halogenated compounds in accordance with the well known and typical reactions of Ullmann, Friedel and Craft, Wurtz, Reformatski and others. Aluminium under such conditions also acts as a strong pyrogenetic and neutral reducing agent.

Thus it is seen that aluminium powder when properly activated by heating in a current of pure dry hydrogen behaves almost exactly like copper, silver, mercury or zinc in most of the typical organic reactions. The only notable exception with regard to the behaviour of aluminium is that it does not form an organo-metallic derivative like magnesium in Grignard's reaction under the same circumstances. Otherwise aluminium powder is a very reactive material with which a large number of organic syntheses can be achieved.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dry Distillation with Aluminium Powder.

In these series of experiments, fine commercial aluminium powder was refluxed with absolute alcohol for several hours and then very thoroughly washed with ether. The metallic powder thus purified was then carefully dried at 110°, and stored in stoppered bottles until required for use. For the purpose of dry distillation

a hard glass tube about 30 inches in length was bent at about 8 inches from one end, so as to form a delivery tube to which a distilling flask was attached as a receiver. This latter was carefully cooled by cold water, ice or freezing mixtures according to the nature of the compound undergoing distillation. The longer portion of the tube was packed to about three quarters of its length with broken pumice which had been previously coated with the prepared aluminium dust. The rest of the tube at the other end was filled with the substance intimately mixed with three times its weight of the same aluminium powder. A slow stream of pure and carefully dried hydrogen or carbon dioxide was then passed through the tube while the latter was heated in a combustion furnace, taking care to heat the substance last of all. In this way many substances were distilled and all the various products isolated and identified. The results are summarised in tabular form.

Dry distillation with aluminium powder in a current of dry hydrogen or carbon dioxide.

Substance.	Temperature of distillation.	Main product of reaction and percentage of yield (in brackets).	Bye-products.
Phenol	470°	Benzene (21)	Diphenyl.
Catechol	500°—540°	Benzene (15)	Phenol, diphenyl.
Resorcinol	„	„ (19)	„ „
Quinol	„	„ (12)	„ „
Pyrogallo	„	„ (12)	Catechol, phenol, diphenyl.
Phloroglucinol	„	„ (13)	Resorcinol, phenol, diphenyl.
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	„	Aniline (23)	Benzene, ammonia, <i>p</i> -aminophenol.
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	„	„ (20)	Benzene, ammonia, <i>m</i> -aminophenol.
<i>p</i> -Nitrosophenol	„	„ (21)	Benzene, ammonia, <i>p</i> -aminophenol.
<i>m</i> -Nitraniline	„	„ (15)	Benzene, ammonia, <i>m</i> -phenylene diamine.

Substance.	Temperature of distillation.	Main product of reaction and percentage of yield (in brackets).	Bye-products.
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	500°—540°	Toluene (26)	Ammonia, <i>p</i> -toluidine.
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	„	Aniline (13)	Benzene, ammonia, carbon dioxide.
Salicylic acid	„	Benzene (15)	Phenol, diphenyl, carbon dioxide.
Benzoic acid	„	„ (15)	Diphenyl, carbon dioxide.
Benzaldehyde	„	Toluene (39)	<i>Nil</i>
Phthalic anhydride	Dull red heat	Phthalide (83)	<i>Nil</i>
Quinone	„	Benzene (13)	Phenol, diphenyl.
Succinimide	„	Pyrrrol (17)	<i>Nil</i>
Benzophenone	„	Diphenylmethane (43)	<i>Nil</i>
β -Naphthol	„	Naphtbalene (35)	<i>Nil</i>
β -Naphthaquinone	„	„ (21)	β -Naphthol
Anthraquinone	„	Anthracene (30)	<i>Nil</i>
Phenanthraquinone	„	Phenanthrene (35)	<i>Nil</i>
Alizarine	„	Anthracene (37)	<i>Nil</i>
Isatin	„	Indol (20)	Aniline
Indigo	„	„ (12)	„

ULLMANN'S REACTION WITH ALUMINIUM POWDER.

(a) *Diphenyl from Iodobenzene.*

In this and all other subsequent experiments described in this paper the aluminium powder immediately before use was heated in a stream of pure, dry hydrogen for about half an hour.

Iodobenzene (10 g.) and aluminium powder (5 g.) were heated under reflux at 250° for about three hours. A vigorous reaction took place and some iodine was deposited in the neck of the flask. The viscous reaction product was extracted with ether, filtered from the unchanged aluminium powder, decolorised with sodium thiosulphate, and allowed to evaporate, when colourless crystals, m.p. 70° were obtained. These were identified to be those of diphenyl (yield 0.43 g.).

(b) *Dibenzyl from Benzyl Chloride.*

A mixture of benzyl chloride (10 g.) and aluminium powder (5 g.) was heated under reflux at 200° for about an hour. A vigorous reaction took place and the mass became yellow. On extraction with ether, filtration and slow evaporation a yellow crystalline solid was obtained which melted at 51°, and was identified to be dibenzyl (yield 4.2 g.).

(c) *Adipic Acid from β -Iodopropionic Acid.*

β -Iodopropionic acid (6 g.) was intimately mixed with aluminium powder (2.2 g.) and the mixture first heated at 110°-120° for one hour and then at 180°-200° for three hours. The product was cooled and extracted with boiling water. On cooling the extract, large shining colourless crystals separated out. These were filtered off and recrystallised from boiling water, when the substance melted at 148°, and was identified to be adipic acid (yield 1.4 gm.).

(d) *Diphenylamine from Aniline and Chlorobenzene.*—Chlorobenzene (10 g.), aniline (9 g.) and aluminium dust (5 g.) were heated at 180°-200° for about three hours. The cold reaction product was then extracted with ether, the ethereal extract filtered from unchanged aluminium powder and allowed to evaporate when a solid crystalline substance was obtained. This on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 52°, and was identified to be diphenylamine (yield 3.5 g.).

(e) *Diphenylether from Phenol and Bromobenzene.*—A mixture of phenol (9 g.), bromobenzene (17 g.), aluminium powder (6 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g.) was heated at 180°-200° for about four hours. The reaction product was then distilled in steam, when an oily liquid with a fine flowery smell came over in the distillate. It was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract thoroughly washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and water, dehydrated with calcium chloride and the ether evaporated when a pale yellow liquid was obtained boiling at 252° which was identified to be diphenyl ether (yield 15 gm.).

(f) *Hexachloroethane from Carbon Tetrachloride.*—Carbon tetrachloride (15 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux with aluminium powder (7 g.) for about half an hour. A vigorous reaction took place and dense white fumes evolved which condensed in the neck of the flask to a colourless crystalline solid. The reaction pro-

duct was isolated by extraction with ether and purified by recrystallisation from benzene when it was obtained in large colourless crystals with a camphor-like smell and melting at 185°. It was identified to be hexachloroethane (yield 9.3 gm.).

FRIEDEL-CRAFT'S REACTION WITH ALUMINIUM POWDER.

(a) *Acetophenone from Acetylchloride and Benzene.*—A mixture of carefully dried acetylchloride (10 g.) and benzene (15 g.) was treated with aluminium powder (6 g.) and the whole heated on the water-bath under reflux for about three hours. Torrents of hydrogen chloride were evolved and the mixture set to a dark viscous mass. The product was then carefully treated with ice cold dilute hydrochloric acid when the dark aluminium compound dissolved and a pale yellow oil having the characteristic odour of acetophenone separated out. It was extracted with benzene, dried with calcium chloride and fractionated when a colourless oil boiling at 202° was obtained. This was identified to be acetophenone (yield 9.5 gm.).

(b) *Diphenyl Methane from Benzyl Chloride and Benzene.*—A mixture of benzyl chloride and benzene was treated with aluminium powder as in the above instance and the product similarly isolated. It was a colourless oil boiling at 174°-176° and with a pronounced orange-like smell. It was identified to be diphenylmethane (yield about 38 %).

(c) *Triphenylmethane from Chloroform and Benzene.*—A mixture of pure dry chloroform (30 c.c.) and benzene (100 c.c.) was treated with aluminium powder (5 g.) and the whole heated on the water-bath for about one hour. A vigorous reaction took place and a copious stream of hydrogen chloride was evolved. After the reaction was over the dark brown aluminium compound was decomposed with ice cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the upper benzene layer separated. This was dried and then distilled, at first on the water-bath at ordinary pressure to remove the excess of benzene, and then over a free flame under reduced pressure (8 mm.). Three fractions were obtained, namely :

(1) A pale yellow oil—3.7 gms. (identified as diphenyl methane).

(2) A colourless crystalline solid—8.6 gms. (identified to be triphenylmethane).

(3) A dark coloured residue—2.7 gms. (which could not be identified).

(d) *Triphenyl Methane from Carbon Tetrachloride and Benzene.*—A mixture of carbon tetrachloride (30 g.), benzene (100 g.) and aluminium powder (7 g.) was gently heated on the water-bath under reflux, when a vigorous reaction took place and torrents of hydrochloric acid gas were evolved. In about ten minutes the reaction was over and the whole mass became dark brown in colour. The product was cooled, decomposed with ice cold dilute hydrochloric acid, and from the benzene layer thus separated, diphenylmethane (yield 3.7 g.) and triphenyl methane (yield 11.2 g.) were isolated and identified.

(e) *Benzophenone from Benzoyl Chloride and Benzene.*—A mixture of benzoylchloride (15 g.) and benzene (50 g.) was treated with aluminium powder (5 g.) and the mixture heated on the sand-bath under reflux, till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased (about 4 hours). The mixture was then treated with ice cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the benzene layer separated as usual. This was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and water, dried and fractionally distilled at ordinary pressure, when an almost colourless oil boiling at 300°-310° was obtained. This solidified in the receiver and on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 46°, and was identified to be benzophenone (yield 3.2 gm.).

Reformatski's Reaction with Aluminium Powder.—A mixture of acetophenone (12 g.), bromoacetic ester (17 g.), aluminium powder (5 g.) and dry benzene (100 c.c.) was gently warmed on the water-bath until a vigorous reaction took place. The latter was allowed to subside and then the mixture gently boiled on the sand-bath for about two hours. After cooling, ice cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added to decompose the dark coloured aluminium compound, the benzene layer separated, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and water, dried and then fractionally distilled under highly reduced pressure. A colourless liquid boiling at 120°/4 mm. was obtained which was identified to be β -phenylmethyl-hydroxy-propionic ester. (yield 6.2 g.).

NEUTRAL REDUCTION WITH ALUMINIUM POWDER.

(a) *Phenyl-hydroxylamine and Aniline from Nitrobenzene.*—A mixture of nitro-benzene (20 g.), ammonium chloride (6 g.), distilled water (250 c.c.) and aluminium powder (16 g.) was vigorously agitated while being cooled in a freezing mixture. A vigorous reaction took place and in about an hour the smell of nitrobenzene had

completely disappeared. The solution was filtered at the pump, the residue washed with about 100 c.c. of ice cold water, and the combined filtrate and washings saturated with salt and left standing in the freezing mixture, when the liquid became almost semi-solid with deposit of fine colourless crystals. These were identified to be those of phenyl-hydroxylamine (yield almost quantitative).

The reaction was repeated at the ordinary temperature, and after allowing the reaction mixture to stand for about 12 hours, only aniline (yield 9.2 g.) could be isolated. There was no trace of phenyl-hydroxylamine. The solution was faintly alkaline to litmus, and the odour of ammonia could be detected.

(b) *Triamido-phenol from Picric Acid.*—Picric acid on similar treatment to the above, at first gave picramic acid (yield 87%) and then triamido-phenol (yield 63 per cent.).

(c) *Benzhydrol from Benzophenone.*—Benzophenone was similarly treated in 75 % alcoholic solution with aluminium powder, and after about 12 hours a quantitative yield of benzhydrol was obtained in colourless crystals, m.p. 168°.

(d) *Aniline and Triaminobenzene from Chrysoidine.*—Chrysoidine on similar treatment gave an almost theoretical yield of a mixture of aniline and triamino-benzene (1 : 2 : 4).

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